

On-farm evaluation of an improved rice variety and integrated weed management techniques for improving the productivity of deepwater rice

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Weeds are a major biological constraint to yield in most rice-growing areas of the world. Unlike the periodic outbreaks of insect pests and plant diseases, weeds are ever present and threatening. The problem is critical in deepwater rice fields. Fields are generally dry at seeding, become moist with rain, and are finally flooded. The various conditions in this rice environment, from upland to flooded, are suited to a wide range of weeds, including upland, lowland, and aquatic weed types. A single method of weed control is not enough under these situations. Favorable rice cultivars with good weed competitiveness are desirable so that farmers' inputs can be minimized and their incomes maximized (Nantasomsaran and Moody 1995). Management practices including land preparation, time of seeding, plant population, and fertilization can increase the competitive ability of rice and enable it to better suppress weed growth. Integrated weed management by the rational use of indirect and direct weed control methods may control weeds effectively and reduce the total cost of weed control. Thus, several indirect and direct methods can be combined in a given situation in terms of net benefits (Ampong-Nyarko and De Datta 1991).

On-farm participatory trials were carried out during the wet seasons of 2004 and 2005 in typical deepwater rice environments in five villages of Ersama Block in Jagatsinghpur District of coastal Orissa, India. The relative contribution of an improved (recommended) variety and integrated weed management (IWM) techniques to grain yield and economic returns to deepwater rice was compared with that of traditional weed management practices adopted by farmers with traditional (local) rice varieties. Four treatment combinations (see table) were laid out in a randomized complete block design in 10 farmers' fields (two farmers from each village). An area of 200 m² was considered as one treatment plot and each farmer's field with an area of 800 m² was considered as one complete block. Improved deepwater variety (IV) Durga (tall, long duration, and photoperiod-sensitive) and local variety (LV) Bhaluki (semitall, long duration, and photoperiod-sensitive) were directly sown during the first week of June under both weed management practices. The IWM techniques included one deep plowing 1 mo before sowing, followed by removal of stubbles and weeds manually, preparation of a stale seedbed by shallow tillage 1 fortnight before

Yield performance and economics of deepwater rice as influenced by variety and weed management techniques (pooled data, 2004 & 2005).

Treatment ^a	Plant height (cm)	Ear-bearing tillers (no. m ⁻²)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Weed dry weight (t ha ⁻¹)	Gross returns (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Net returns (Rs ha ⁻¹)	Benefit-cost ratio
LV + TWM	117	139	1.15	2.98	1.04	5,792	62	1.01
LV + IWM	126	179	1.52	4.10	0.26	7,720	200	1.03
IV + TWM	111	167	1.73	4.28	0.57	8,632	2,302	1.36
IV + IWM	134	223	2.96	5.32	0.11	13,968	5,848	1.72
CD (P=0.05)	2.4	11.2	0.58	0.72	0.07	–	–	–

^aLV = local variety; IV = improved variety; IWM = integrated weed management techniques; TWM = traditional weed management practices.

sowing to allow the surface weed seeds to germinate with a premonsoon shower, followed by final land preparation through shallow tillage prior to sowing. Rice was sown in rows 20 cm apart behind a plow with a seed rate of 80 kg ha⁻¹. A moderate dose of P₂O₅ and K₂O (20 kg ha⁻¹) was applied at sowing. The N fertilizer (30 kg ha⁻¹) was applied 21 d after sowing (DAS). Pretilachlor at 600 g ha⁻¹ was applied at 3 DAS to suppress the initial weed growth, followed by postemergence application of 2,4-D sodium at 750 g ha⁻¹ at 30 DAS to control broadleaf weeds. Traditional weed management (TWM) involved the broadcast method of seeding with a high seed rate of 100–120 kg ha⁻¹ for maintaining a high rice plant population to suppress weeds at the early growth stages and one manual weeding at the later stage of crop growth (60–70 DAS) for the removal of broadleaf and aquatic weeds.

The dry weight of weeds was recorded from a quadrat of 1 m² at the peak flowering stage of the crop (20 wk after sowing). Grain and straw yield of rice along with yield components were recorded at harvest. Economic data were calculated based on the price of the produce in the local market and wages prevalent in the area.

The IV Durga performed better and outyielded the LV Bhaluki with both IWM and TWM practices, but the response was greater with the former techniques (see table). The highest grain yield (2.96 t ha⁻¹) was recorded with Durga with the adoption of IWM techniques. This yield reflected lower weed dry matter (0.1 t ha⁻¹), better rice plant growth, and significantly more fertile tillers than Bhaluki.

Across weed management treatments, Durga gave 76% more grain than Bhaluki. The adoption of IWM techniques enhanced rice grain yield by 56% compared with TWM, suggesting a potential net profit of Rs 5,848 ha⁻¹ due to the adoption of IWM techniques. Adoption of IWM compared with traditional practices increased grain yield by 71% in IV Durga, whereas this was only 32% for LV Bhaluki. The yield enhancement of rice was 157% in the treatment in which Durga was grown with IWM techniques in comparison with that in which Bhaluki was grown with TWM practices. This indicates the importance of choosing a suitable variety and weed management techniques to get the maximum yield advantage in a deepwater rice environment. Further studies are required to determine the role of more weed-competitive rice cultivars in improving the productivity of traditional systems. This study, however, suggests that improved cultivars may give greater yields and better weed suppression than local cultivars.

The highest cost of cultivation (Rs 8,120 ha⁻¹) was recorded in the treatment where IWM techniques were adopted with IV Durga. But, the better yield in the same treatment plots gave a higher net return (Rs 5,848 ha⁻¹) than in the other treatment plots. The highest benefit-cost ratio of 1.72 was obtained from the same treatment. The adoption of IWM practices using local varieties appeared to offer little advantage. Adopting IWM techniques with an improved variety would, however, enable farmers to get more benefits from deepwater rice cultivation.

This study shows that the selection of appropriate varieties is an important component for maximizing the economic benefits from the adoption of IWM techniques and for improving the productivity of deepwater rice.

References

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